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Who participates in Continuous Vocational Education and Training and why do they do it?

Wuttke, Eveline

Chair of Business and Economic Education/Goethe University Frankfurt, wuttke@em.uni-frankfurt.de

Seeber, Susan

Chair of Business Education and Human Resource Development/Georg-August-University Goettingen, susan.seeber@wiwi.uni-goettingen.de

Abstract

Demographic, political and technological trends cause an increasing shortage in skilled labor in specific economy sectors (health care, hotel/restaurant industry, trade, technology) in most industrialized European countries (Cedefop, 2016). Consequently, companies/employers are forced to fill a rising number of job vacancies with currently unexploited labor force potential (e.g. unqualified/low qualified people, people returning from career breaks or those with migration background as well as older employees and unemployed people). On the other hand, there is still a substantial number of non-working people of employable age (potential additional labor force, Eurostat, data extracted in May 2017), especially if we look at the groups mentioned above. Hence, to ensure participation in working life and to provide companies with sufficient workforce, CVET (Continuous Vocational Education and Training) measures are essential. CVET can be defined as the continuation or resumption of more or less organized learning after the completion of a first education phase. Previous studies usually focus on attendance figures. Taking the results of these studies into account, it shows that some groups of employees are underrepresented. However, little is known about the motivation to attend CVET or what motivates companies to offer trainings, especially for our target groups.

In part of our studies (interview study and quantitative survey), we refer to all four sectors (see above) of the economy. In a vignette study we concentrate on health care and hotel/restaurant industry. In these two sectors there is the most severe shortage of skilled workers, which is true for most European countries. Furthermore, many people belonging to our target groups work in these sectors without being adequately qualified.

1 Introduction

As early as 2013, many sectors had struggled with hard-to-fill vacancies (Brenzel et al. 2014; particularly the health and social services sector, the hotel and restaurant industry, and the retail and technology sectors; Czepek et al. 2015). Reasons are:

- 1 Demographic changes in most industrialized nations lead to a decrease in qualified workforce (Cedefop, 2015).
- 2 Structural changes: A decline in jobs in the manufacturing sectors is accompanied by new jobs in secondary service sectors; the demand for qualified workers will increase (Helmrich et al. 2016, p. 73).

- 3 Technological changes and digitalization lead to changes in work processes and technologies, requiring employees to continuously improve their qualification (Brynjolfsson & McAfee 2014).

If vacancies cannot be filled by hiring qualified personnel from the labor market, companies must develop other strategies to cover their demand for skilled labor. Particular attention is being directed toward groups that, have not been the focus of companies' (further) training activities and are thus underrepresented in continuous vocational education and training (CVET; e.g., persons without prior vocational training, persons with (longer) employment interruptions or with a migration background, and older workers).

The aim of our study is to identify group-specific and sector-specific causes for, as well as barriers against, CVET measures. Here, we discuss the employees' point of view. Two questions will be answered:

1. What are reasons for and barriers against CVET within marginalized or special target groups (older employees, people with no/low previous qualification, people re-entering the labor market, and those with a migration background)?
2. What types of training would be preferred by members of these target groups?

2 Clarification of CVET, marginalized groups and industry sectors as constructs

CVET is defined as Education/training after initial education and training or after entry into working life aimed at helping individuals to improve/update their knowledge/skills, acquire new skills or continue their personal or professional development (Cedefop 2008, p. 50).

It can be divided into individual, in-company, occupation-related and nonoccupational training (Autorengruppe Bildungsberichterstattung 2018, p. 175).

Continuing education plays an important role in "shaping successful occupational biographies, active participation in society in general and the realisation of a self-desired way of life" (Seeber et al. 2017, p. 21). Offerhaus, Leschke & Schömann (2010) point out that participation in CVET is often determined by age, origin, employment status, level of qualification or education. Such factors are - singularly or in combination - CVET barriers for certain groups of people (marginalized groups; Seeber et al. 2017). *Marginalized groups* include:

- Employees with low or no formal qualification, employees of a subordinate social value (Schulte-Braucks 2013) or those who do not have a (recognized) vocational qualification.
- Returnees to the labor market who have had a greater employment interruption than the statutory parental leave.
- Persons with a migration background, who were born either abroad or have at least one parent that was born abroad (Konsortium Bildungsberichterstattung 2006).
- Older persons aged 55 and over who are able to work but are only sometimes involved in working processes (Cedefop 2015, p. 92).

We focus on *four industry sectors*, namely, retail, health care, hotel/restaurant trade and technology, because these sectors currently have problems with vacancies that cannot be filled.

3 Short summary of the state of research on participation in CVET among the target groups

Research on training causes and barriers has so far been primarily descriptive and used standardized questionnaires to query individual and contextual factors that promote and hinder training participation (e.g., Gorges 2013; Kaufmann & Widany 2013; BMBF 2017; Gorges & Hollmann 2015). The following statements can be summarized:

For *employees with a migration background*, participation in CVET in Germany showed a positive trend between 2010 and 2012, then stagnated for some years and rose significantly by 2016 (up to 40%). However, the participation rate in CVET by employees with a migration background still falls below the one for persons without a migration background (51%) (Autorengruppe Bildungsberichterstattung, 2018). Lower participation is mainly explained by costs of CVET and time restrictions but also by childcare obligations and a lack of a sense of necessity of CVET (Riesenfelder et al. 2011, Barz & Tippelt 2018). In addition, a lack of adequate courses (in terms of time and content) and missing certificates (Brüning 2002) or language difficulties can be barriers as well (Desjardins 2015).

Employees with low or no formal qualification are particularly underrepresented in CVET (Bilger et al. 2013). Frequently these employees attend only if it is mandatory (Gillen et al. 2010) or if participation is driven by the expectation that the achieved qualification will improve performance at the workplace, secure the job/position or provide opportunities for advancement (Schröder et al. 2004, Bilger et al. 2013) and/or higher income (Käpplinger et al. 2013). At the same time, however, interest in the respective content plays a role in deciding for or against participation (Bilger et al. 2013). Costs and cost-benefit-consideration are barriers (Krenn 2010). Furthermore, competing (private or job-related) obligations and training offers outside of working hours restrict participation (Gillen et al. 2010; Käpplinger et al. 2013).

Participation rates for *older employees* show a positive trend over the past few years (cf. Autorengruppe Bildungsberichterstattung 2018, p. 174). The main reasons provided by this group for participating in CVET are social exchange, as well as interest in the respective contents covered in CVET (Tippelt et al. 2009a; Friebe & Schmidt-Hertha 2013). Another reason is the desire to improve one's own abilities in order to better understand new developments as well as the improvement of general or job-related knowledge (Tippelt et al. 2009b, Bilger et al. 2013). Barriers in this population include that older employees do not see a benefit in learning new things (Wooden et al. 2001; Pfeifer et al. 2012), and that the CVET offer does not fit one's own needs (Schröder & Gilberg 2005; Tippelt et al. 2009a).

There are few studies on training participation by people reentering work life. In this group, women are usually the focus because this population is predominantly comprised of women who have longer periods without employment (Dieckhoff & Steiber 2009). The main reasons provided for participation are the desire to return to work well prepared, the expansion of knowledge or a desired occupational change.

The outlined studies mention central causes and barriers without, however, systematically looking at the groups of employees and the sectors that we have in focus.

4 Method

4.1 Interview study

We use a mixed method approach with an interview study, a vignette study and a quantitative survey. This paper focuses on results of the interview and vignette studies.

72 interviews were conducted with employees from our target groups (see Table 1; for detailed descriptions of the interviews and the results see Siegfried et al. in print).

Table 1: Sample interview study

	Employees (with):	Migration background	Low/no formal qualification	Aged 50 or over	Reentering <u>worklife</u>	Total
		(N=14)	(N=21)	(N=26)	(N=12)	(N=72)
Gender and age	Female	5	10	20	12	47
	Male	9	11	6		25
	Age (SD)	31.29 (8.20)	35.95 (11.05)	56.27 (4.22)	39.83 (6.52)	42.97 (12.94)
Sector	Retail	3	7	6	5	21
	Health	--	5	11	4	20
	Restaurant	8	5	5	2	19
	Technology	3	4	4	1	12

The interviews were transcribed and coded (Mayring, 2016). The coding guideline consists of 30 main categories and 42 subcategories (for more detail cf. Siegfried et al., in print). Coder training resulted in satisfying interrater reliabilities (Cohen's kappa .70 - .85).

4.2 Vignette study

Vignettes model decision-making situations that are close to real life decisions and capture individual preferences (Atzmüller & Steiner, 2010). We selected training topics that are highly relevant to employees within a respective sector, for example, pain therapy and dementia management in health care and vegetarian-vegan cuisine as well as complaint management in the hotel/catering trade. We further implemented variations in the options concerning the timeframe (half-day vs. full-day; the total duration is kept constant), the organization (presence seminar vs. web-based/blended learning) and the design (external vs. internal seminar).

In focused interviews (Merton, Fiske & Kendall, 1990) participants were asked to read the description of the catalogues and then decide which option they would prefer along with reasons for their decision. Individual preferences for a design variant were recorded on a three-step scale.

So far, the results from 15 participants (table 2) are available. Coding was performed in accordance with the design variants (see above). Coder training resulted in satisfying interrater reliabilities (Cohen's kappa .85 - .89).

Table 2 Sample vignette study

	Employees (with):	Low/no formal qualification	Migration background	Reentering <u>worklife</u>	Total
		(N=2)	(N=9)	(N=4)	(N=15)
Gender and age	Female	1	3	2	7
	Male	1	6	2	8
	Age (SD)	46.5 (2.5)	38 (6.38)	43 (6.04)	42.97 (12.94)

5 Findings

5.1 Findings of the interview study

The analyses of causes and barriers for continuing training as well as possible differences between the various employee groups and sectors were carried out descriptively and on the basis of ANOVAs. Four groups were used for the analyses: (1) Employees with a migrant background and (2) with a migrant background and low or no formal qualification, (3) persons re-entering employment and (4) older employees.

In sum, the results show that there are similarities in reasons and barriers for all groups (see Siegfried et al., in print). In the case of occupation-related CVET, occupational changes account for most of the responses across all groups (54-92% of persons in each group). Another reason mentioned by employees across all groups was a desire for further development and maintenance of more general knowledge (65-100% of persons per group). In terms of barriers, all groups mention inappropriate offers as a main barrier (29-75% employees per group), as well as competing occupational obligations (23-50% employees per group).

Nevertheless, it is also possible to uncover group-specific characteristics that could only be revealed through targeted questioning, which confirms the methodological approach of our study:

1. The safeguarding of the current occupational situation is mentioned significantly more often by persons with a migration background and those returning to work than by all other groups.
2. Refreshing occupation-related knowledge is more often a reason for further training among re-entrants than for the other target groups.
3. Private competing obligations represent the biggest barrier to participation in CVET, especially for re-entrants.
4. The lack of a sense of need is primarily mentioned by people with a migration background and especially by people with a migration background and low formal qualifications.

Looking at possible differences between the sectors, it is particularly interesting to note that in some cases the abovementioned training causes and barriers have other weightings than the addressee-specific analysis (see Siegfried et al., in print).

5.2 Findings of the vignette study

With the situational approach, we expected even more differentiated insights into the reasons and obstacles to participate in CVET and to obtain ideas for the type of further education measures that are suitable for specific groups.

Figure 1 Reasons and barriers to participate on CVET vignettes

The analyses of both reasons for and barriers against CVET as well as the individual preference for the different CVET options were carried out descriptively. 40% of participants prefer the first option of the given CVET vignettes, since it is organized as one full-day training session. The participant argued that a block training has the advantage of an intensive training session, along with the ability to leave their workplace and concentrate on the content of the seminar. Interestingly, most participants are positive about the possibility to flexibly organize their time in a blended-learning approach. However, many point out that they lack the discipline to do so and would therefore rather not attend such a seminar. Therefore, 60% of the participants voted for sessions organized as a blended-learning unit as their last choice.

Apart from the different seminar options, the participants explained that their decision to attend the CVET was based on the importance of the content presented in the training (73%), the possibility to gain more self-confidence (27%) and because they receive a certificate (47%). Moreover, they point out, that the methods announced were interesting (expert lecture (80%), exchange of experience (93%), group work (73%), role play (80%)). However, some participants argued against participation in the trainings presented in the vignettes. Reasons included topics being of little interest (27%), fear that too little practice would be addressed (20%) and the cost of accommodation/meals (40%).

Furthermore, we asked the participants to describe—if they had free choice—what kind of CVET they would like to attend. The participants mentioned different topics of interest, such as product training, basic courses (how to hold a tray), sales training, stress management and trainings regarding legal issues.

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Biographical notes

Eveline Wuttke is Professor of Economic and Business Education at Goethe University in Frankfurt. Her research activities are in the area of learning from errors at school and at work, professional development of business and economics teachers, domain specific competence measurement in vocational education, economic competence/financial literacy and CVET. She has a leading role in recent research projects funded by the German Federal Ministry of Education and research. Eveline Wuttke has been a member of various national and international scientific communities for many years and is reviewer for a broad range of scientific journals and for conference papers.

Susan Seeber is Professor of Business Education and Human Resource Development at Goettingen University. Her research activities are in the area of large scale assessment in VET, measurement of vocational competences, and social disparities in the access to VET and CVET. She has a leading role in recent research projects funded by the German Federal Ministry of Education and research. Susan Seeber has been a member of various national and international scientific communities for many years and is reviewer for a broad range of scientific journals and for conference papers. She furthermore is a member of the author group of the national report on education for the chapters on VET and CVET.